

**ЗВ'ЯЗОК МІЖ ЗМІНАМИ КОНЦЕНТРАЦІЇ МАЛОНОВОГО
ДІАЛЬДЕГІДУ ТА ПОКАЗНИКАМИ ЛІПІДНОГО СПЕКТРУ КРОВІ У
ПАЦІЄНТІВ З СТАБІЛЬНОЮ ІШЕМІЧНОЮ ХВОРОБОЮ СЕРЦЯ ТА
СУПУТНЬОЮ АРТЕРІАЛЬНОЮ ГІПЕРТЕНЗІЄЮ**

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CHANGES IN CONCENTRATION OF
MALONIC DIALDEHYDE AND BLOOD LIPID SPECTRUM INDICATORS
IN PATIENTS WITH STABLE CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND
CONCOMITANT ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION**

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Coronary heart disease (CHD) and concomitant arterial hypertension (AH) are key issues in modern cardiology. At the base of atherogenesis, which plays a crucial role in the progression of both pathologies, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction lie. It is the result of an imbalance between prooxidant and antioxidant factors. The involvement of oxidative stress in atherosclerosis is reflected in lipid peroxidation (LPO), which is initiated and maintained by oxidized metabolites generated by atherogenic cells themselves. Oxidized LDL cholesterol plays a key role in the occurrence and development of atherosclerosis. Reactive oxygen species can also damage vascular endothelium and reduce nitric oxide secretion, leading to increased endothelial dysfunction manifested by increased vasoconstriction, hypercoagulation, and smooth muscle cell proliferation. Laboratory markers for checking the progression of these processes are the concentration of total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and malonic dialdehyde (MA). Evaluating the relationship between changes in the levels of these indicators can be a promising direction in the diagnosis of CHD and AH and will help improve and optimize drug treatment.

The aim of the study. To identify an association between changes in malonic dialdehyde concentrations and total cholesterol and low-density lipoproteins in patients with stable coronary heart disease with and without concomitant hypertension.

Materials and methods of research. The study included 131 patients with stable CHD and AH. Patients were divided into 2 groups: 1) 80 patients with stable CHD and concomitant AH; 2) 51 patients with stable CHD without concomitant AH. In the study, we evaluated fluctuations in MA levels. The lipid spectrum of the blood was assessed by the level in the serum of total cholesterol, LDL.

The obtained results and their discussion. The level of MA in the group of patients with concomitant hypertension is significantly higher. We found a weak direct correlation between MA and total cholesterol, MA, and LDL in the group of patients with coronary heart disease with concomitant hypertension. We found a weak inverse correlation in patients without abnormal blood pressure fluctuations.

Conclusions. We were able to establish a relationship between changes in the concentration of MA and total cholesterol and LDL in patients with stable CHD with and without concomitant AH, which confirms the significant effect of oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction, which are integral companions of hypertension on the blood lipid spectrum.